

Use of Potassium Bromate : Bromination of Halobenzenes and Halobenzoic Acids

AMALENDU BANERJEE, GOPAL CHANDRA BANERJEE, SACHCHIDANANDA DUTT,
(Mrs.) SANTA BANERJEE^a and HARAPRASAD SAMADDAR^b

Chemistry Department, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700 032

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Syntheses of bromo compounds by the bromination of halobenzenes and halobenzoic acids using potassium bromate under acidic condition have been discussed.

THE bromination of aromatic compounds still holds its charm to the synthetic organic chemists as is evident from the recent works of Mckillop and Bromley¹. The use of potassium bromate under acidic condition for oxidation of benzaldehyde² as well as bromination of benzoic acid³ and benzene⁴ has been reported. This method is economical, time saving, simple and avoids the possible hazards of using elemental bromine. It involves the dropwise addition of an aqueous solution of potassium bromate to the boiling mixture of the benzene derivatives in (8*N*) sulphuric acid with or without glacial acetic acid for approximately one and a half hours. Only trace of bromine is evolved in most of the cases. Derbyshire and Waters⁵ used elemental bromine and potassium bromate as catalyst for similar bromination. The reaction mixture is worked up by the method described before^{3,4}. Thus, chlorobenzene has been brominated to furnish a mixture containing 1-bromo-4-chlorobenzene (80%) and 1-bromo-2-chlorobenzene (20%). 1,4-dichlorobenzene gives two products viz. 1-bromo-2,5-dichlorobenzene and very small amount of an unidentified compound, m.p. 147°, whereas 1,4-dibromobenzene produces only 1,2,4-tribromobenzene (30%). The expected 5-bromo-2-chlorobenzoic, 4-bromo-3-chlorobenzoic and 3-bromo-4-chlorobenzoic acids are obtained in fair yields from 2-chlorobenzoic, 3-chlorobenzoic and 4-chlorobenzoic acids respectively. Also 2,5-dibromobenzoic acid is obtained from 2-bromobenzoic acid and the same product 3,4-dibromobenzoic acid is obtained from both 3-bromo³ and 4-bromobenzoic acids in similar yields. It is observed that the use of acetic acid as solvent improves the yields of the desired bromo-products and in each case unreacted starting material can be recovered. Iodobenzene furnishes 1-bromo-4-iodobenzene under similar condition with probably iodoxybenzene as an additional product and 2-iodobenzoic acid produces probably 2-iodoxybenzoic acid. Further work in this line is in progress.

Experimental

A.R. acetic acid was heated under reflux for six hours with excess of potassium dichromate and distilled just before use. Pure potassium bromate, sulphuric acid and distilled water were used whenever needed. Gas liquid chromatography was carried out with a Hewlett Packard 5730 A gas chromatograph with flame ionisation detector using H.P. recorder model 7127A. Resolution was performed on a stainless steel column (1.83 m × 3 mm of 3% of SE-52 on sil. RUB (100-120 mesh) at 180°. The N.M.R. spectra have been mostly taken in 90 MHz.

1. General Procedure for the Bromination of Halobenzenes :

Potassium bromate solution (10 ml of water per g of the reagent) was added dropwise in course of thirty minutes to the boiling mixture of the required amount of sulphuric acid (8*N*), distilled glacial acetic acid and the halobenzene. The reaction mixture was further heated under reflux for one hour, cooled and poured onto iced-water. The organic material was extracted with chloroform, washed successively with water; saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate and water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent was removed from a steam bath. The residue, on fractional distillation under reduced pressure, furnished the bromohalobenzene. Thus, the following compounds were prepared :

(A) *1-Bromo-4-chlorobenzene and 1-bromo-2-chlorobenzene* : Distilled chlorobenzene (22.5 g), glacial acetic acid (200 ml), sulphuric acid (8*N*; 160 ml) and potassium bromate (16.7 g in 160 ml of water) after the aforementioned reaction condition yielded a gummy yellow oil (20.0 g), b.p. 193°, which on crystallisation from ethanol furnished

(a) Chemistry Department, Dinabandhu Andrews College, Garia, 24-Parganas, West Bengal.

(b) Chemistry Department, Ramakrishna Mission Residential College, Narendrapur, 24-Parganas, West Bengal ; Teacher Fellow (U. G. C.), Chemistry Department, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700 032.

colourless flakes (10.0 g ; 52%) of 1-bromo-4-chlorobenzene, m.p. 67°^{6a}. [δ (CCl₄), 7.20 (H_{3,5}, d ; J=7H_z) and 7.43 (H_{2,6}, d ; J=7H_z) p.p.m.]. After separation of the *para* compound, the mother liquor afforded a liquid (9.5 g), b.p. 82°/10 mm. The vapour phase chromatography of this material revealed the presence of the *ortho* isomer when compared with the pure *para* compound and it indicated the formation of a mixture containing 20% *ortho* and 80% *para* isomer in the overall bromination step.

(B) *2-Bromo-1,4-dichlorobenzene* : A mixture of 1,4-dichlorobenzene (29.4 g), distilled glacial acetic acid (200 ml), sulphuric acid (8N ; 170 ml) and potassium bromate (16.7 g in 170 ml of water) after refluxing for ninety minutes followed by usual working up furnished (i) starting material (17.8 g), b.p. 175-180°, (ii) the desired material as a yellowish oil (9.8 g ; 43%), b.p. 79-80°/1 mm, [δ (CCl₄), 7.22 (H₅, d, d ; J=2, 7H_z), 7.37 (H₆, d ; J=7H_z) and 7.65 (H₃, d ; J=2H_z) p.p.m.] and a small amount of pot-residue which on boiling with activated charcoal in ethanol yielded needles, m.p. 147°, (to be investigated further).

(C) *1,2,4-Tribromobenzene* : Pure 1,4-dibromobenzene (4.7 g, m.p. 87°), glacial acetic acid (25 ml), sulphuric acid (8N ; 16 ml) and potassium bromate (1.67 g in 16 ml of water) under similar condition furnished a viscous liquid (0.9 g ; 30%), b.p. 100-105°/3 mm, which solidified on cooling and crystallised from ethanol as needles. m.p. 44°^{6b}, m/e 312, 314, 316, 318 (M⁺), 233, 235, 237 (M-Br), 154, 156 (M-2Br). The starting material was recovered as a forerun during the distillation (3.9 g) b.p. 210-220°, which solidified on cooling, m.p. 87°^{7a}.

(D) *1-Bromo-4-iodobenzene* : A mixture of distilled iodobenzene (40.8 g), glacial acetic acid (200 ml), sulphuric acid (8N ; 170 ml) and potassium bromate (16.7 g in 170 ml of water) after ninety minutes' refluxing produced (i) chloroform soluble product and (ii) chloroform insoluble product. The former, after the usual work up and removal of the solvent, furnished unreacted iodobenzene (12.8 g), b.p. 185-190°^{7a} and an oil (7.0 g), b.p. 102°/2 mm, which on boiling with ethanol and activated charcoal produced colourless flaky crystals of 1-bromo-4-iodobenzene (6.3 g ; 23%), m.p. 92°^{6b}, m/e 282, 284 (M⁺), 155, 157 (M-I). The aqueous layer, obtained after the extraction with chloroform, was found to deposit large amount of silky white precipitate which on filtration followed by successive washing with water, saturated aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution and alcohol produced a colourless solid (5.5 g ; 16%), m.p. 222° (decomposed with explosion). This material, presumably iodoxybenzene^{6b}, was estimated⁸ to be of 95% purity. This is under further investigation. When acetic acid was omitted in this experiment, the yield of the probable iodoxy compound increased to 32% while the yield of the desired bromo compound remained unchanged.

2. General Procedure for the Bromination of Halobenzoic Acids :

The following bromohalobenzoic acids were obtained by the aforementioned method and the cold reaction mixture was poured onto iced-water and usually worked up with chloroform to furnish acidic material which was weighed (to calculate the approximate extent of bromination) and esterified with ethanol and concentrated sulphuric acid in the usual way. The crude mixture of esters, thus obtained, was worked up and distilled under reduced pressure to separate into its components. The esters were subsequently hydrolysed to isolate the starting acids and the bromoderivatives for their identification.

(E) *5-Bromo-2-chlorobenzoic Acid* : A mixture of 2-chlorobenzoic acid (10.0 g), sulphuric acid (8N ; 100 ml) and glacial acetic acid (25 ml) was heated under reflux for ninety minutes with the dropwise addition of potassium bromate (8.4 g in 100 ml of water). The resulting crude acid (11.8 g ; the increase in weight indicated 40% bromination) was esterified and worked up in the usual way to furnish (i) low boiling fraction (8.8 g), b.p. 102-4°/1 mm, [δ (CCl₄), 1.40 (CH₂CH₃, t ; J=7H_z), 4.37 (CH₂CH₃, q ; J=7H_z), aromatic H at 7.23 (H₃, d, d ; J=2, 7 H_z), 7.40 (H_{4,6}, complex, m) and 7.79 (H₅, d ; J=d, 2, 7 H_z) p.p.m.] which on hydrolysis with potassium hydroxide produced an acid, m.p. 137° ; m.m.p. with authentic 2-chlorobenzoic acid^{7b} remained undepressed and (ii) the desired material (4.5 g ; 27%), b.p. 128-30°/1 mm, [δ (CCl₄), 1.40 (CH₂CH₃, t ; J=7H_z), 4.33 (CH₂CH₃, q ; J=7H_z) ; aromatic H at 7.27 (H₃, d ; J=7H_z), 7.50 (H₄, d, d ; J=2, 7H_z) and 7.90 (H₅, d ; J=2H_z) p.p.m.] which on alkaline hydrolysis in the usual way gave 5-bromo-2-chlorobenzoic acid^{9a}, m.p. 155-6°, Neutral Equivalent (N.E.) was found to be 233±3. The acid could not be decarboxylated in the usual way.

(F) *4-Bromo-3-chlorobenzoic Acid* : In a similar method 3-chlorobenzoic acid (7.8 g), sulphuric acid (8N ; 120 ml), acetic acid (50 ml) and potassium bromate (12.6 g in 120 ml of water) yielded the crude acid 10.0 g ; 55% conversion), which was esterified, worked up and distilled under reduced pressure to yield (i) low boiling ester (3.7 g), b.p. 104-14°/1 mm, [δ (CCl₄), 1.38 (CH₂CH₃, t ; J=7H_z), 4.35 (CH₂CH₃, q ; J=7H_z), 7.42 (H_{4,5}, m ; complex), 7.90 (H₆, d, d ; J=8, 2 H_z) and 7.97 (H₂, t ; J=2-3 H_z) p.p.m.] which on alkaline hydrolysis produced an acid, m.p. 157-8°, m.m.p. with authentic 3-chlorobenzoic acid^{7b} remained undepressed, and (ii) high boiling bromo ester (4.9 g ; 39%), b.p. 133°/1 mm, [δ (CCl₄), 1.41 (CH₂CH₃, t ; J=7H_z), 4.38 (CH₂CH₃, q ; J=7H_z), 7.29 (H₃, d, d ; J=2, 7 H_z), 7.60 (H₅, d ; J=7H_z) and 7.77 (H₂, d ; J=2H_z) p.p.m.] which on hydrolysis

produced 4-bromo-3-chlorobenzoic acid^{9a}, m.p. 218°, N.E. 230±5, in excellent yield.

(G) *3-Bromo-4-chlorobenzoic Acid*: 4-Chlorobenzoic acid (10.0 g), sulphuric acid (8N; 250 ml), acetic acid (50 ml) and potassium bromate (25.0 g in 250 ml of water) furnished the crude acid (12.0 g; 40% conversion) which was esterified, worked up and distilled to produce (i) ester of the starting acid (8.1 g), b.p. 95-97°/1 mm, [δ (CCl₄), 1.39 (CH₂ CH₃, t; J=7H_z), 4.34 (CH₂ CH₃, q; J=7 H_z), 7.34 (H_{3,5}, d, d; J=2, 9 H_z) and 7.92 (H_{2,6}, d, d; J=2, 9 H_z) p.p.m.] which on hydrolysis furnished the unreacted acid^{7b}, m.p. 236° and (ii) high boiling bromo ester (3.6 g; 22%), b.p. 125-27°/mm, [δ (CCl₄), 1.40 (CH₂ CH₃, t; J=7H_z), 4.34 (CH₂ CH₃, q; J=7H_z), 7.41 (H₅, d; J=7H_z), 7.86 (H₆, d, d; J=2, 7H_z) and 8.21 (H₂, d; J=2H_z) p.p.m.] which on hydrolysis produced in good yield, 3-bromo-4-chlorobenzoic acid^{9a}, m.p. 214°, N.E. 233±3.

(H) *2,5-Dibromobenzoic Acid*: Similarly 2-bromobenzoic acid (4.0 g), sulphuric acid (8N; 35 ml), acetic acid (50 ml) and potassium bromate (3.5 g in 35 ml of water) gave the crude acid (4.8 g; 51% conversion) which was esterified, worked up and distilled to produce (i) a low boiling ester (1.3 g), b.p. 124-30°/6 mm, [δ (CCl₄), 1.38 (CH₂ CH₃, t; J=7H_z), 4.32 (CH₂ CH₃, q; J=7H_z), 7.27-7.77 (4H; aromatic; m) p.p.m.] which on hydrolysis produced 2-bromobenzoic acid^{7b}, m.p. 150°, m.m.p. with starting material remained undepressed, and (ii) the desired high boiling fraction (2.5 g; 43%), b.p. 153°/4 mm, [δ (CCl₄), 1.40 (CH₂ CH₃, t; J=7H_z), 4.36 (CH₂ CH₃, q; J=7H_z), 7.43 (H_{3,4}; complex, m) and 7.83 (H₆, d; J=2H_z) p.p.m.] which on hydrolysis produced 2,5-dibromobenzoic acid^{9b}, m.p. 157°, N.E. 275±5.

(I) *3,4-Dibromobenzoic Acid*: Potassium bromate (12.5 g in 125 ml of water) was added dropwise to a refluxing mixture of 4-bromobenzoic acid (8.0 g), sulphuric acid (8N; 125 ml) and glacial acetic acid (100 ml). The crude acid (9.4 g; 46% conversion) thus obtained, was esterified and worked up to furnish (i) ethyl 4-bromobenzoate (3.9 g), b.p. 137°/5 mm, [δ (CCl₄), 1.38 (CH₂ CH₃, t; J=7H_z), 4.35 (CH₂ CH₃, q; J=7H_z), 7.53 (H_{3,5}, d; J=8H_z) and 7.83 (H_{2,6}, d; J=8H_z) p.p.m.] which on hydrolysis produced the starting 4-bromobenzoic acid^{7b} m.p. 251°, and (ii) high boiling dibromo ester (4.2 g; 34%) b.p. 149°/3 mm., [δ (CCl₄), 1.37 (CH₂ CH₃, t; J=7H_z), 4.33 (CH₂ CH₃, q; J=7H_z), 7.62 (H₅, d), 7.66 (H₆, d, d; J=2, 9H_z) and 8.18 (H₂, d; J=2H_z), p.p.m.] which on hydrolysis produced 3,4-dibromobenzoic acid^{9b} in

good yield, m.p. 234°, N. E. 276±5, m.m.p. with the authentic 4-bromobenzoic acid, prepared by neutral permanganate oxidation of *p*-bromo-toluene, was found to be 200-213° with previous shrinking at 190° and with authentic 3,4-dibromobenzoic acid⁹ remained undepressed.

(J) *2-Iodoxybenzoic Acid*: Potassium bromate (8.4 g in 85 ml of water) was added dropwise to the refluxing mixture of 2-iodobenzoic acid (13.5 g), sulphuric acid (8N; 85 ml) and glacial acetic acid (50 ml). The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for ninety minutes and attempted to work up with chloroform in the usual way but the acidic product was insoluble in chloroform. This was filtered through Buchner funnel and air-dried to furnish an acid (14.0 g), m.p. 222° (decomposed with explosion); N. E. 278±2. This is under further investigation.

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